

Grain yield losses due to rats at Kurukshetra, India, 1984.

Block	Village	Fields observed (no./village)	Variety	Av cut tillers/m ²	Grain loss (g/m ²)	Yield loss (t/ha)
Thanesar	Shadipur	25	Jaya	47.5	308.8	3.1
	Kanipla	15	Jaya	34.5	224.1	2.2
	Kanpur	18	PR106	28.6	185.7	1.9
	Hinga Kheri	11	PR106	13.2	87.8	0.9
Shahabad	Kalsani	16	PR106	8.7	56.6	0.6
	Nagla	13	Jaya	18.0	117.0	1.2
Pehowa	Sandhali	10	IR8	5.2	33.8	0.4
	Saina Saida	15	PR106	12.5	81.2	0.8
	Gumthala	22	Jaya	30.2	196.0	2.0
Cheeka	Sonthi	14	Jaya	6.4	41.3	0.4
	Kakkahri	12	Jaya	8.0	52.0	0.5

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Water management

Supplementary irrigation of upland crops following rice

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We studied the supplementary irrigation requirement of rabi pulses and oil seeds

grown in residual moisture following rice on slightly sloping land.

Crops were sown on 16 Dec 1985. Mungbean was harvested on 18 Mar, urdbean on 25 Mar, and peanut on 1 Apr 1986. A total 77.4 mm of rainfall was received during crop growth. The groundwater table remained at about 80 cm depth (78-83 cm) during the cropping season.

Peanut performed best under residual moisture without irrigation, yielding about 0.7 t/ha (Table 1). One irrigation at flowering almost doubled peanut

yield to 1.4 t/ha. Further irrigation did not result in any significant increase in yield.

Total supplementary water used was 77.4, 127.4, 177.4, and 227.4 mm in the treatments of no irrigation, 1 irrigation, 2 irrigations, and 3 irrigations, respectively (Table 2). □

Table 1. Grain yield of crops following rice under different moisture regimes. New Delhi, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Peanut	Mungbean	Urdbean	Mean
Residual moisture	0.71	0.11	0.15	0.32
Irrigation at flowering	1.36	0.10	0.18	0.54
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation	1.28	0.12	0.19	0.53
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation + pod elongation	1.36	0.18	0.17	0.54
Mean	1.18	0.09	0.17	—
LSD (0.05) for moisture regimes for crops				0.08
for 2 crops under Same moisture regime				0.11
for 2 moisture regimes for same crop or different crops				0.22
				0.18

Table 2. Irrigation requirement under different moisture regimes. New Delhi, India.

Treatment	Irrigations (no.)	Water applied (mm)		Total water needed (mm) including rainfall
		Irrigation	Rainfall	
Residual moisture	0	0	77.4	77.4
Irrigation at flowering	1	50	77.4	127.4
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation	2	100	77.4	177.4
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation + pod elongation	3	150	77.4	227.4

Effect of water regime on yield and water use of rice

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We studied the effect of three water regimes on yield and water used for evapotranspiration (ET) during 1985 kharif (Jun-Oct) at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° 3' E). Treatments were continuous submergence of 5±1 cm and static water tables at 30 cm and 60 cm depths below soil surface.

The experiment was carried out in 3 replications in field-installed RCC tank lysimeters 1.8 × 1.5 m area and 1.5 m depth filled with Beni silty clay loam series (Mollisol) soil of Pantnagar. Soil had 9% sand, 61% silt, and 30% clay; pH 6.3; cation exchange capacity 20.0 meq/100 g; bulk density 1.33 g/cm³; 3.4% organic matter; retained 34.6% moisture at 1/3 bar and 11% at 15-bar tension; and hydraulic conductivity of 0.82 cm/h. ET was calculated from daily change in water table (considering soil

Rice yield and evapotranspiration (ET) under different irrigation treatments. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Treatment	Yield (kg/2.7 m ²)		ET (mm) during different growth phases ^a				Water use efficiency (kg/ha-mm)
	Grain	Straw	Vegetative	Reproductive	Ripening	Total	
Continuous submergence	1.91	2.33	368 (54)	222 (33)	92 (13)	682	10.4
Water table at 30 cm	1.54	1.90	268 (56)	168 (35)	44 (9)	480	11.9
Water table at 60 cm	1.36	1.53	248 (70)	90 (25)	19 (5)	357	14.1
LSD (0.05)	0.29	0.45					

^aVegetative = 10 wk, reproductive = 6 wk, and ripening = 2 wk. Figures in parentheses are percent of total.

porosity) or change in submergence level and replenished accordingly. Rainfall contribution was accounted for. The total 1,990 mm rainfall received was well distributed over the growing season.

Continuous submergence gave significantly higher grain yield than water tables maintained at 30 cm and 60 cm depths (see table). But water use efficiency was highest with 60 cm water table and least with continuous submergence (see figure).

The rate of water used as ET was

highest in continuous submergence and depended a great deal on rainfall in any particular week. Water use was lowest with 60 cm water table and intermediate with 30 cm water table. The differences in ET became more pronounced later in the season.

The total water use as ET with continuous submergence was nearly double that with 60 cm water table. In all treatments, a major portion of total water was used during the vegetative

Weekly rainfall (mm)

Evapotranspiration behavior of rice under different water regimes. Uttar Pradesh, India.

phase; only one-fourth to one-third was used during the reproductive phase. With the 60 cm water table, more than two-thirds total ET was during the vegetative phase. □

Farming systems

Intercropping of pulses with rainfed rice at South Coastal Orissa, India

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We studied a feasible rice-based intercropping system to assure grain yield in at least one crop in case of erratic monsoon or other natural calamity. Under favorable climatic conditions, the additional income from an intercrop would augment earnings of small and marginal farmers.

Single crop rice (Parijat) was sown at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Green gram (K851), black gram (T9), peanut (AK12-24), red gram (Upas 120), and cowpea (C152) were sown as intercrops in rice: intercrop proportions of 1:1 (20 cm), 1:2

Grain yield of rice and intercrops. Berhampur, India.

Intercropping system	Yield (t/ha)			Return (\$/ha)		
	Main crop (rice)	Intercrop	Total	Main crop	Intercrop	Total
Rice + green gram	1.2	0.26	1.43	232	128	360
Rice + black gram	1.3	0.39	1.78	254	192	446
Rice + peanut	1.1	0.67	1.72	299	358	657
Rice + red gram	0.9	0.36	1.26	179	223	402
Rice + cowpea	1.1	0.40	1.51	221	214	435
Monocrop rice	2.2	**	2.23	444	**	444
Intercrop mixture						
1:1	1.7	0.50	2.22	**	**	**
1:2	1.0	0.59	1.63	**	**	**
2:1	0.9	0.32	1.25	**	**	**
2:2	0.7	0.41	1.13	**	**	**
LSD (0.05)	**	**	ns	**	**	**

(20,60 cm), 2:1 (20,60 cm), and 2:2 (20,60 cm), in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 5.60, 0.21% organic C, 18 kg available P/ha, and 227 kg exchangeable K/ha. Rice received 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha in 2 splits; pulses received 20-40-0 kg NPK/ha as basal.

Single crop rice produced 2.23 t/ha (see table). The rice yield was affected to different degrees by the intercrop. Highest rice yield was in rice + black gram at all proportions.

In the intercrops, peanut yielded the most (0.67 t/ha). The 1:2 intercrop resulted in higher intercrop yields (0.59 t/ha). □